

USE OF RENEWABLE ELECTRICITY

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It is clear to all of us that our need for electricity on a global scale is increasing day by day. If we take the last five years, the world's electricity demand is increasing by 50% every year. This requires the increase and development of alternative energy types. If we pay attention to the information of the International Energy Agency, if the use of solar energy develops at such a pace, by 2050, it will be possible to meet 25% of the world's electricity needs at the expense of solar energy, and it will be possible to reduce the carbon dioxide gas released into the environment by 6 billion tons per year.

Renewable energy is energy collected from renewable sources that replenish naturally over time. It includes sources such as sunlight, wind, water movement and geothermal heat. While most renewable energy sources are sustainable, some are not. For example, some biomass energy sources are considered unsustainable in their current operation. Renewable energy often generates energy to generate electricity for the grid, air and water heating and cooling, and self-contained energy systems.

From 2011 to 2021, renewable energy has grown from 20% to 28% of the global electricity supply system. Fossil energy decreased from 68% to 62%, and nuclear energy from 12% to 10%. The share of hydropower decreased from 16% to 15%, while solar and wind energy increased from 2% to 10%. Biomass and geothermal energy grew between 2% and 3%. 135 countries have installed 3,146 gigawatts, while 156 countries have developed laws regulating the renewable energy sector. There are more than 10 million jobs globally related to the renewable energy industry. Among them, solar photovoltaic is the largest employing system of renewable energy sources.

Today, the process of energy production in renewable energy systems is carried out much faster and more efficiently. Therefore, the price of energy is

decreasing, and their share in the total energy consumption is increasing. Most of the new electricity installed worldwide is from renewable sources. Photovoltaic solar energy or wind energy has already become the cheapest source of electricity in many countries.

Many countries around the world have renewable energy sources. Renewable energy accounts for more than 20% of their total energy supply. And some generate more than half of their electricity from renewable energy sources. Several countries generate almost all of their electricity using renewable energy. National renewable energy markets are expected to continue to grow strongly in the 2020s and beyond. Studies have shown that a global transition to 100% renewable energy is feasible in all sectors - power, heat, transport - and is economically very beneficial. The implementation of renewable energy and energy efficiency technologies will have significant benefits in the areas of energy security, climate change and the economy. However, renewables continue to be hampered by fossil fuel subsidies. During the study of international public opinion, it has been proven that renewable sources such as solar energy and wind energy are sufficient to meet the needs of the population. Therefore, the International Energy Agency said that in 2021, more efforts should be made to increase renewable energy sources, and until 2030, the production of these sources will be approximately He emphasized the increase by 12%.

Renewable energy technology projects are usually large-scale, but they are also suitable for rural, remote areas and developing countries where energy is often crucial to human development. Because most renewable energy technologies are powered by electricity, renewable energy is often used interchangeably with the term electrification. China will account for almost half of global renewable electricity growth in 2021. Unlike fossil fuels (oil, natural gas, etc.), renewable energy is not used up faster than it takes to replenish it. Significant opportunities for renewable energy and energy efficiency are available over large geographic areas, unlike other energy sources that are concentrated in a limited number of countries. Rapid implementation of renewable energy and energy efficiency, technological diversification of energy sources will significantly benefit energy security and the state budget economically. Nowadays, the cost of solar and wind energy has become much cheaper. In some cases, switching to these sources is becoming cheaper than continuing to use current fossil fuels. It also reduces environmental pollution, such as air pollution caused by burning fossil fuels, and improves public health.

It would reduce premature deaths from pollution and save trillions of dollars in health care costs each year. Many analyzes of decarbonization strategies have shown that implementing the above strategies with health benefits can significantly reduce costs.

The continued decline in the cost of renewable energy equipment, such as wind turbines and solar panels, will lead to an increase in the use of renewable energy sources. The government's new cost containment policies helped the industry weather the global financial crisis better than many other sectors. According to the International Renewable Energy Agency, the total share of renewable energy sources (including power, heat, and transportation) in this century in the industry will need to be "better than" (less than 2.0 °C (3.6 °F)) the increase in average global temperature compared to previous levels. taking) should grow six times faster. Home solar panels and batteries can often be used for that home or combined with other homes if connected to the grid. More than 44 million households use home-produced biogas for lighting or cooking. And more than 166 million households have started using the new generation of more efficient biomass stoves. According to the study, a country needs to reach a certain point in its growth before using renewable energy. Ban Ki-moon, the eighth Secretary-General of the United Nations, noted that renewable energy has the ability to lift the poorest countries to a new level of prosperity. At least 30 countries around the world have more than 20% of their energy supply from renewable sources. Renewable energy often replaces four sectors that use conventional fuels: electricity generation, hot water, transportation, and agricultural (off-grid) energy services. By 2021, more than a quarter of electricity will be produced from renewable sources.

Solar water heating is an important contribution to renewable heat sources in many countries, especially in China. In China, most of these systems are installed in multi-family residential buildings. In China, this energy source meets part of the hot water needs of approximately 50-60 million households. Total solar water heating systems installed worldwide meet part of the water heating needs of more than 70 million households. In Sweden, the use of biomass energy has surpassed oil-based energy sources. Heat pumps provide water heating and cooling. Nowadays, renewable heat energy is also growing rapidly. About 10% of the energy used for water heating and cooling comes from renewable sources. One move to decarbonize transportation is the increased use of electric vehicles (EVs). Less than 4% of transport energy comes from renewable sources.

Economical use of fuel sources mechanical energy, therefore, electrical energy striving to reduce the cost of acquisition, continuously Wind is a renewable energy source using energy on a large scale came Energy of Uzbekistan at the present time 19,000 industrial, 80,000 agricultural, 19 thousand communal and 3.5 million households provides consumers with energy.

The sun's rays reach the earth every year, equal to $62 \cdot 10^{16}$ kWh of energy. brings energy. 60 percent of this energy is the earth's atmosphere, 25.5 percent is the ocean and sea, 14.5 percent will be spent on land heating. 2.5 percent of it is mechanical wind to energy, 0.14 percent to mechanical energy of river movement, 0.12 percent to various fuel wood, peat, coal, oil and chemical energy of combustible shale becomes If we take into account that the cross-sectional area of the Earth is $127.6 \cdot 10^6$ km², the energy of falling sunlight is $176.6 \cdot 10^{12}$ kW, that is, to the earth in one year $1.56 \cdot 10^{18}$ kWh $\approx$ $1.6 \cdot 10^{18}$ kWh solar energy falls.

The golden rays of the sun are 150,000 billion kilowatt hours of wind per year to our earth energy, 33,000 billion kWh of water energy. And in the forests 220,000 billion kilowatt-hours of energy are collected annually due to sunlight. From this besides, due to solar energy, it has been huge on earth for thousands of years energy reserves are accumulated. For example, it lies in the lap of our planet 3,580,000 billion kWh in coal, 480,000 billion kWh in peat, combustible 700,000 billion kWh of energy in shale, 80,000 billion kWh of energy in natural gas stock available. At present, humanity uses one thousandth of these huge reserves per year uses even less than Today, the sun is a giant nuclear reactor similarity is known, in which a nuclear reaction occurs at high pressure and temperature. As a result of this reaction, hydrogen turns into a helium nucleus, and the sun the temperature in the active zone of the reactor exceeds 10 million degrees.

This reaction in the sun producing 560 million tons of helium per second released 4 million tons of hydrogen converts into energy. The sun far from using energy they have tried in the past. Ancient Greek scientist Archimedes of the sun light through a system of mirrors, burning the ships of the Romans write in the history that he sent left Outside of solar energy countries on a large scale is being used. of Northern France Physic-chemist Felex in Odeysda Sun led by Tremba power plant was built, and its power 1100 kW, the temperature that generates and reaches 3800 degrees. 1816 Robert Stirling of Iceland powered by a solar device had created the solar engine. 1954 American Ges Repot and Bruce

The skins are directly exposed to sunlight ease of use of the aircraft expressed his opinion. 20 years later Later, London confirmed the correctness of this idea College researchers in practice proved.

In short, Alternative Energy Harvesting shows that today's factories can use a lot of electricity. This will pave the way for the development of our country's economy. All these energies are renewable energies. Although each of these are small power plants, their useful operating coefficients are smaller than NPP, IES, HPP, but they are distinguished by their environmental cleanliness. Through this, we distinguish the environment with ecological purity and economic activity.

Therefore, today, the use of solar energy is the most optimal and ecologically clean type of energy. Although solar energy is theoretically harmless to the environment, its use has the potential to change the albedo of the Earth's surface. At present, the amount of energy received from the Sun is unlikely to change the albedo, because the amount of energy consumed by the Sun is very small.

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